

Transforming Waste into Opportunity: Tackling Municipal Solid Waste Challenges in Buanbuawuha Sub-City, Dessie, Ethiopia

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Abstract

Municipal Solid Waste Management (MSWM) is a global problem, particularly in developing countries like Ethiopia, where inadequate infrastructure and poor practices exacerbate environmental and public health challenges. In Dessie, Buanbuawuha sub-city, rapid urbanization has strained MSWM systems, causing environmental hazards. A mixed-methods approach gathered data, capturing insights on current MSWM system. Geographic Information System (GIS) mapped the spatial distribution of illegal municipal solid waste (MSW) disposal practices across sub-city areas. Key findings indicate that average MSW generation rate is approximately 0.53 kg/person/day, which would result in 22,470 tons MSW per year in Buanbuawuha sub-city. Organic waste constitutes over 40% of the total waste generated, highlighting its significant share in the MSW stream. Notably, more than 80% of the MSW produced in the area has the potential for reuse, either as recyclable material or as a source of energy. Open dumping remains a prevalent issue, with over 78% of households disposing of MSW in ditches and along roadsides. Only about 21% of households have access to formal communal collection services, and even then, 63.2% of them reported irregular collection schedules, just once a week. The lack of adequate MSWM caused the proliferation of 18 illegal and permanent dumping sites throughout the sub-city. This study highlights the urgent need for strategic investments in MSWM. By integrating sustainable practices and promoting resource recovery, Buanbuawuha can transform waste from an environmental threat into an asset, fostering resilience and enhancing public well-being.

Keywords: *Municipal Solid Waste Management, Waste generation rate, Illegal dumping, Waste disposal site.*

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Introduction

MSWM has emerged as a cornerstone of human well-being and environmental sustainability,

alongside essential services like water and electricity. Inadequate and unsatisfactory solid waste management practices, particularly at landfills, pose a multitude of environmental and

health risks including, the proliferation of flies, unpleasant smell and leachate contamination(Boateng et al., 2016). Globalization and urbanization is one of the primary causes of the escalating MSW crisis, particularly in developing countries(Couth & Trois, 2011). MSWM stands as a paramount concern among these environmental issues, as the production of MSW has been an inescapable consequence of human settlement since the dawn of civilization, impacting both developed and developing nations (Adedara et al., 2023).

MSW has become a significant issue globally, with the problem being especially acute in developing countries(Buenrostro et al., 2001), including Ethiopia. In these regions, 30-50% of urban residents lack access to proper MSWM services, often resorting to unsafe disposal practices(Cudjoe et al., 2020). Additionally, common MSWM systems in developing countries are plagued by a variety of issues, including limited collection coverage, inconsistent collection services, crude open dumping and burning without proper pollution control measures, and the proliferation of disease-carrying insects (Debrah et al., 2021).

In developed nations, MSWM systems are generally well-established and effective, with high collection rates, proper disposal methods, and extensive waste reduction and recycling programs (Hettiarachchi et al., 2018). In contrast, developing countries face a multitude of challenges in managing MSW, including insufficient infrastructure, constrained financial resources, weak institutional capacity, and a lack of public awareness(Hirpe & Yeom, 2021). Some studies also found that illegal dumping and open burning are common MSW disposal practices in Africa, which pose serious environmental and health risks (Arsiso et al., 2017; Kumar et al., 2017; Laurieri et al., 2020).

Improper MSW disposal presents a significant danger to the environment and public health in developing countries resulting in air pollution, water contamination, soil degradation, and the transmission of diseases(Joseph et al., 2020). Similarly, the shortage of proper MSW disposal infrastructures has led to increased health risks for residents, with exposure to hazardous

substances and disease-causing pathogens(Yong et al., 2019).

In Ethiopia, MSWM practice is in its rudimentary stage and need extensive effort from the government as well as from the urban dwellers both in terms of funding, technology, capacity building, awareness creation and community participation as well as innovative local means to address the health threat posed by weak MSWM practices (Rupani et al., 2019). In numerous towns throughout Ethiopia, MSWM is very weak and the wastes are dumped along roadsides and in open spaces, which poses a significant risk of creating a serious public health issue and threatening well-being of the peoples (Erasu et al., 2018). Therefore, to address poor-MSWM practice, multifaceted approaches should include; solid waste reduction strategies, improved MSW collection and transportation systems, sustainable discarding practices, and public awareness campaigns (Misganaw, 2023).

To our knowledge, there was no research being conducted on a specific sub city of Dessie. Although numerous studies have been carried out on to understand the MSWM practices and challenges in Dessie Town. Some focused on MSW generation rate(Rai Sharma et al., 2013), or identifying solid waste disposal site(Amanuel Belete et al., 2024) using geospatial technology or recommending alternative solid waste disposal sites(Kebede & Ayenew, 2023), or the management problem of the existing MSW open dumping site in the town(Belayneh et al., 2015). These studies will contribute greatly to the fight to eliminate the ever-increasing solid waste by showing alternative disposal sites. But they don't show the ways to handle MSW starting from generation until disposal and alternative MSWM in the growing solid waste production. And they have not shown the importance of society engagement either. The scattered MSW are usual in various areas of Buanbuawuha sub-city, Dessie. The heaps of MSW are illegally discarded in open spaces, beside roads, within sewage channels, and drainage systems, where they eventually flow into the nearby river. Therefore, this study will highlighted the need for effective solid waste collection systems, proper solid waste disposal facilities, and community participation in SWM activities.

Figure 2. Area and Population of Buanbuawuha Sub-City Kebeles

Survey Design

From the total population of 116,155 in the Buanbuawuha sub-city, a sample size of 400 households was selected. This approach was guided by scientific statistical methods, with a 95% confidence level (Onyeka et al., 2015). The particular equation utilized for calculating the sample size was:

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2} \quad (1)$$

Where, n is the sample size, N is the population size, and e is the level of precision.

The sample was proportionally allocated across the five kebeles by using stratified random sampling. The sample distribution was carefully designed to reflect the demographic proportions of each kebele (KOTHARI, 1990). The specific formula as follows:

$$n_i = \frac{N_i}{N} \times n \quad (2)$$

Where, n_i is sample size for kebele i, N_i is population of kebele i, N is total population and n is total sample size.

This approach increases the accuracy and reliability of the findings. The sample size of each kebele is listed in Table 1.

Table 1. Sample Size in Each Kebele Based on Stratified Random Sampling

Kebele Name	Population	Sample Size	Percentage
Borkena	30,113	104	26
Megenagna	26,441	91	22.75
Ayer-Tena	16,151	55	13.75
Seferes-selam	28,992	100	25
Tita	14,458	50	12.5

A well-organized questionnaire was designed to gather data on key aspects of household MSWM,

including solid waste generation, composition, storage, collection services, and awareness levels.

This comprehensive approach provided a detailed understanding of the entire SWM process from generation to disposal within households.

Interviews

Fifteen key stakeholders, including government officials, waste management authorities, and community representatives, were purposively selected for interviews. This ensured the inclusion of diverse voices and a detailed understanding of the stakeholders' responsibilities and roles.

Geographic Information System (GIS) Data

GIS technology was leveraged to map the distribution of permanent illegal dumping sites in the study area. The coordinates of these solid waste dumpsites were collected through field surveys using a handheld Global Positioning System (GPS) device to record the X and Y coordinates of each site. These coordinates were then imported into ArcGIS 10.8 as a text file and subsequently converted into a shape file to visualize the locations and spatial distribution of the illegal permanent dumping sites. The mapped locations were overlaid with the results identifying improper solid waste dumpsites caused by poor management practices. The findings provided valuable insights into variations in SWM practices and revealed the spatial patterns of illegal dumping across the study area.

Data Processing and Analysis

Quantitative data were examined through descriptive and inferential statistics, incorporating ANOVA, with statistical significance established at $p < 0.05$, using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) (version 27). Descriptive statistics summarized the fundamental aspects of the data, presenting a clear understanding of solid waste generation rates and their composition. At the same time the total solid waste generation rate report for the three consecutive years from the sub-city is also included and analyzed to compare the survey finding. ANOVA tests were used to identify statistically significant differences in solid waste generation across different socio-economic strata. This analysis provided insights into the relationship between socioeconomic status and solid waste generation patterns. For spatial analysis, GIS tools (ArcGIS 10.8) were employed to conduct identify permanent illegal solid waste disposal sites. Qualitative data from interviews were analyzed thematically. Thematic analysis identified recurring themes and patterns in the qualitative data, providing rich insights into community perceptions, attitudes, and practices related to SWM. The mixed-methods approach facilitated the triangulation of findings, which strengthened the validity and reliability of the overall analysis. Triangulation entails analyzing and contrasting results from various data sources to strengthen the reliability of the research.

Results and Discussion

Characteristics of Respondents

Table 2. Socio Economic Characteristics of the Respondents in Buanbuawuha Sub-City

Socio Economic Characteristics	Criteria	No of Respondents	Percentage
Sex	Female	249	62.25
	Male	151	37.75
Age	18-25	104	26
	26-35	142	35.5
	36-45	144	36
	Above 45	10	2.5
Education	No Formal Education	14	3.5
	Primary School (grade 1-8)	129	32.25
	Secondary School (grade 9-12)	106	26.5
	Diploma	140	35
	Degree and Above	11	2.75

Number of Family in the Household	1-3	161	40.25
	4-6	158	39.5
	7-9	54	13.5
	10 and Above	27	6.75
Average Monthly Income in US\$/household	less than \$50	57	14.25
	\$50.1-100.0	102	25.5
	\$100.1-150.0	101	25.25
	\$150.1-200.0	128	32
	Greater than \$200.0	12	3
Occupation of Household leader	Unemployed	53	13.25
	Private Employee	249	62.25
	Public Employed	98	24.5

The socio-demographic profile of households in Buanbuawuha sub-city offers valuable insights for MSWM planning. This study was conducted across 400 households to examine the social and demographic traits of the participants as shown in Table 2. The respondents are predominantly female making up 62.25% of the group, and relatively young with the largest age group 36%, cover within the 36-45 years range, followed by those aged 26-35. These characteristics indicate a community well-suited (WORLD BANK, 2018) for active participation in MSWM initiatives, such as recycling, segregation, and effective disposal programs, provided they are effectively engaged and educated (Abubakar et al., 2022). While some respondents have attained a diploma 35% indicating a reasonable level of formal education that could facilitate the understanding and adoption of structured SWM practices (Saseanu et al., 2019). Primary education and secondary school graduates is suggesting that educational outreach and awareness campaigns should be tailored to these levels for maximum impact (Kountouris & Remoundou, 2023).

In terms of household size, the majority of respondents reside in households with 1 to 3 members (40.25%), while the next largest group consists of households with 4 to 6 members (39.5%), the rest are reside in households with 7 or more members. These variations underscore the need for tailored MSWM strategies that consider household size to optimize service delivery and community engagement. The household size distribution provides valuable insights into solid waste generation patterns and potential resource requirements for MSWM.

Regarding to monthly income per household, about 14.25% of households earn less than \$50 per month, emphasizing the need for low-cost or subsidized SWM services to make them accessible and inclusive. Those earning between \$50.1-150 are better positioned to participate in affordable programs like pay-as-you-throw systems or community-based recycling initiatives. Households earning between \$150.1-200 have the potential to adopt more advanced SWM practices, such as composting or waste segregation. However, with only 3% of households earning more than \$200, it is crucial to focus on cost-effective solutions that encourage widespread participation and ensure long-term success in MSWM efforts. The study conducted in Bahirdar city reveals that total income is a key factor influencing households' readiness to make a payment for enhanced SWM services (Wegedie, 2018). This underscores the necessity for cost-effective solutions to encourage participation from various income levels. Similarly, in Liberia emphasizes that income significantly affects households' readiness to pay for upgrade MSW disposal services (Scarlet et al., 2022).

Additionally, the reliance on private sector employment is 62.3%, unemployment rate highlight potential economic instability, which could drive informal solid waste disposal practices. These socio-demographic factors underscore the need for designing inclusive, efficient and community-tailored MSWM.

Number of Family and Monthly Income on MSW

To analyze the relationship between household size and MSW generation, the study calculated

the average daily solid waste generation rate. Similarly, to examine the influence of income on MSW generation, the average monthly income per household member was determined by dividing the household's total monthly income by the number of household members. This approach provides a more detailed understanding of both household size and income levels impact waste generation.

Number of Family versus MSW Generation Rate

Figure 3. Effect of Family Size on the Solid Waste Generation Rate

Figure 3 illustrates that the solid waste generation rate generally decrease with family size. When the family size is small (1 to 3 person), the waste generation rate is approximately 0.73 kg/person/day. As family size further increases to 4 and above, the MSW generation rate rapidly decreases and the average value is around 0.46 kg/person/day. This trend is backed by multiple studies that emphasize the dynamics of MSW generation in relation to household size(Hadiyanto et al., 2019). Additionally, a study in Tikrit found that family size negatively impacts solid waste generation rates, with larger families producing less waste per capita(Al-AbidRaba & Khuthayer, 2012). The data indicates that as number of family grows, the waste generation rate decreases and then level off, possibly due to co-consumption, resource sharing, and centralized waste disposal.

Economic factors and consumption structure may also change with family size and finally reduced the MSW generation rate per capital. Based on the 400 household's investigation, the mean of waste generation rate was 0.53 kg/person/day in Buanbuawuha sub-city.

Several factors influence this difference in MSW generation. The efficiency of resource use and waste-sharing practices in larger families contributes to lower per capita waste(Sivakumar & Sugirtharan, 2012). Furthermore, environmental awareness and income levels play significant roles in solid waste generation, with larger families often having better resource management practices(Herianto et al., 2019). Although larger families produce less MSW per person, they generate a higher total volume of MSW, raising concerns about overall SWM strategies. Tailored approaches are necessary for different household sizes to optimize SWM effectively.

Average Monthly Income versus MSW Generation Rate

Figure 4. Effect of Average Monthly Income on the Solid Waste Generation Rate

Figure 4 illustrates clear positive relationship between average monthly income per person and solid waste generation in kg/person/day. As income increases, so does the amount of MSW produced. Specifically, individuals in the \$10-20

income range generate approximately 0.4 kg/person/day of solid waste, while those earning above \$50 produce about 0.75 kg/person/day. This trend aligns with global patterns, where wealthier populations tend to generate significantly more solid waste. For instance the study in São Paulo, Brazil, indicates that the mean per person income has grown from 10.1 to 13.6 USD per day, which correlates with an increase in per person MSW generation from 0.65 to 0.90 kg/person/day (Pisani et al., 2018). This supports the trend of higher MSW production among wealthier populations. High-income countries can produce up to 1.5 kg of solid waste per person daily, compared to less than 0.5 kg in low-income nations (Roy & Tarafdar, 2022).

This increase in MSW generation can be attributed to greater purchasing power, leading to higher consumption rates of goods and services, as well as lifestyle choices that favor convenience, such as take-out meals and disposable products (Bandara et al., 2007). Additionally, urbanization often accompanies rising incomes, contributing to higher solid waste levels due to denser populations. While wealthier individuals produce more solid waste, they also have better access to recycling and SWM programs, highlighting a complex relationship between income, consumption, and sustainability (Aspet et al., 2022). These insights are crucial for decision-makers seeking to design efficient solid waste reduction strategies, particularly in higher-income brackets, to address the environmental impacts of increased MSW production.

MSW Composition and Generation Rates

The total solid waste generation data from 400 households in Buanbuawuha sub-city indicates that organic waste accounts for the largest share (40.9%, 344.31 kg), with a generation rate of 0.861 kg/household/day. Plastic (19.3%, 162.58 kg), paper (13.0%, 109.2 kg) and ash (12.4%, 104.58kg) follow generating rate 0.406, 0.273 and 0.261 kg per household per day, respectively (Figure 5). Total solid waste generated from the samples is 840.97 kg/day, with an average rate of 2.102 kg/household/day and 0.53 kg/person/day, lower than the Sub-Saharan

Africa mean of 0.65 kg/person/day (Umer et al., 2019). The Sanitation and Beautification Department's report covering three consecutive years (2021-2023) indicates an average MSW generation of approximately 0.49 kg/person/day, increasing from 0.36 kg in 2021 to 0.61 kg/person/day in 2023 (Buanbuawuha, 2021-2023). The results obtained from the surveys in this study are consistent with the department's reports, reinforcing the validity of the findings.

Figure 5. MSW Compositions and Generation Rates at Buanbuawuha Sub-city: (a) MSW Composition; (b) MSW Generation Rate

Although no specific study has been conducted on a single sub-city to quantify solid waste generation, existing research on Dessie Town provides valuable insights that align closely with the overall findings. According to different studies, in Dessie the MSW generation rate per household level is estimated at 0.45

kg/person/day(Sharma et al., 2013), with a substantial proportion consisting of food waste and ash. This is also consistent with our findings with similar MSW generation rate and organic waste (food waste) being predominant components followed by plastic and paper, then by ash. Other studies reveal that Ethiopia's MSW generation rate is 0.38 kg/person/day(Gebrekidan et al., 2024). In Jimma city, the average daily MSW generated per person is 0.55 ± 0.17 kg, primarily composed of food waste(Getahun et al., 2012). Additionally, in Dilla, the average solid waste generation rate for residential households is 0.475 kg/person/day(Fereja & Chemed, 2022). These reports are consistent with our findings. Based on MSW generation rate of 0.53 kg/person/day, the total MSW generated in Buanbuawuha sub-city is about 22,470 tons per year, highlighting the urgent need for robust management interventions.

The predominance of organic waste 40.9% is consistent with findings from other urban studies in Ethiopia, where organic waste typically represents a substantial part of the total(Lu et al., 2020) (Tadele Assefa Aragaw, 2016). However, its lower percentage compared to 60% in Addis Ababa suggests regional differences in consumption patterns and SWM practices(Getahun et al., 2011). More than 50% of the total waste generated is composed of organic waste and ash. The organic waste is particularly suitable for biogas production, also the ash can be used for compost production(Agoud et al., 2024). Additionally, plastics and paper, which make up over 31% of the total solid waste, are largely recyclable. Therefore, over 80% of the MSW generated in the area can be utilized either as a recyclable material or as a source of energy, underscoring the need for tailored SWM strategies in Dessie Town, particularly for organic solid waste and traditional energy practices, to enhance sustainability and resource recovery.

Household Solid Waste Storage and Disposal Practices

As shown in Figure 6, represents a substantial part of households (56.7%) store their solid waste in sacks, followed by (32%) who use

plastic bags. A smaller proportion of households (5.3%) rely on private pits, while (1.5%) uses metal containers. Interestingly, 4.5% indicated they do not know about proper solid waste storage practices. The predominant use of sacks and plastic bags for solid waste storage is a common trend observed across different regions of Ethiopia. A study conducted in the Oromia Regional State found that 58.2% of households used sacks, while 30.7% used plastic bags for solid waste storage(Debela et al., 2020). Likewise, a study in Gondar town reported that 46.7% of households used sacks, and 34.7% used plastic bags(Nega, 2020). These findings align with those observed in the Buanbuawuha sub-city, indicating a need to promote the use of more durable and hygienic storage options.

Figure 6. MSW Storage Practice at Buanbuawuha Sub-City

The heavy reliance on sacks and plastic bags, reflects limited access to formal SWM systems, a trend seen in many developing regions(United Nations, 2021). Improper storage methods like the use of plastic bags, contribute to environmental challenges, including pollution and harm to marine life.

Figure 7 illustrates the MSWM disposal sites in Buanbuawuha sub-city based on the survey. Solid waste disposal practices reveal significant concerns regarding environmental safety. A notable 39.8% of households utilize ditches for solid waste disposal, making this the most prevalent method. Close behind, nearly the same percentage of residents disposes of their solid

waste in temporary communal sites and along riversides or gorges, both of which pose substantial environmental risks. Additionally, 17.5% of households discard their solid waste on roadways, underscoring the persistent challenges related with inadequate SWM in the area.

Figure 7. MSW Disposal Sites at Buanbuawuha Sub-City

The results reflect the pressing necessity for enhancement MSW disposal systems and infrastructure to mitigate environmental and health risks. The high share of households in the Buanbuawuha sub-city disposing of their solid waste in the ditch (39.8%) is concerning and consistent with the challenges faced in other parts of Ethiopia. A study in Mekelle city found that 36.1% of families disposed of their MSW in open areas (Gebremedhn & Raman, 2020), while another study in Gondar town reported that

33.9% did so in open fields or ditch (Gedefaw, 2015).

The significant proportion of households 21.3% disposing of their solid waste at the riverside in the Buanbuawuha sub-city is also observed in other regions. According to the results, nearly 61% of MSW is being discarded near water sources, specifically along the ditches and riversides, including tributaries of the Borkena River. As a result, the river ecosystem could be significantly impacted by leachate from the MSW. A study in the Amhara Regional State found that 15.4% of households disposed of their MSW near water bodies, contributing to the pollution of water bodies (Genati et al., 2021). These findings highlight the necessity for comprehensive SWM strategies that address the improper disposal of solid waste in Ethiopia.

GIS Mapping on MSW Dumping Area in Buanbuawuha Sub-city

In Dessie, the entire city relies on a single open landfill site known as Azewa Gedel (Fig. 8). However, this landfill faces significant management (Amanuel Belete et al., 2024; Rai Sharma et al., 2013). It has not been constructed according to proper landfill standards, and solid waste is disposed of in the area without sorting. The current method of disposal is characterized by open dumping; and is situated in a naturally occurring gully formed by landslides, compounded by inadequate road connectivity. Buanbuawuha sub-city, like any other area, has a duty to use it as final dispose site of solid waste in this area.

Figure 8. Legal Solid Waste Open Dumping Sites in Dessie Town

The absence of inadequate enforcement of regulations, monitoring and lack of a consistent waste disposal system has enabled illegal dumping to become widespread. Swift urbanization and rising population levels have challenged the sub-city's capacity to handle MSW efficiently. As the population increases, the amount of waste produced also rises, putting immense pressure on waste disposal services and prompting residents to look for alternative methods of disposal. As a result, numerous illegal, permanent dumping sites have emerged throughout the sub-city, often located near rivers and roadways (Kebede & Ayenew, 2023). The sub-city has not a selected legal solid waste disposal site, leading to an ongoing accumulation of solid waste. Additionally, 63.2% of residents report that their solid waste is collected only once a week. The rest of them receive service two, three, or more times weekly.

Figure 9. Illegal Dumpsites Sistrubtion in Buanbuawuha Sub-City, Dessie Town

Figure 9 illustrates a total of 18 illegal dumpsites across five kebeles in Buanbuawuha sub-city. These illegal dumpsites were identified through on-spot investigation, observing the sites and gathering information from the local residents. It was approved that the solid wastes had stayed for a long period of time without disposing. Borkena Kebele exhibited the highest concentration, with six illegal dumpsites, followed by Megenagna Kebele with four, Sefereselam Kebele with three, Ayertena Kebele

with three, and Tita Kebele with one. These findings highlight a spatial distribution pattern that may inform targeted interventions for MSWM and cleanup initiatives in these areas. Illegal dumping site is the intentional disposal of solid waste in unauthorized locations, including roadsides, near water bodies, and in public spaces (Biru Debalke & Endalew Admas, 2022). Despite the presence of at least 20 illegal solid waste dumps in the sub-city, 18 of these are situated within its boundaries. Among them, 11 are found in open areas along the roadside, 2 near the river, and the remaining near small water bodies and open spaces. Other studies also indicated that illegal dumping sites are commonly situated along roadsides and riverbanks (Du et al., 2023). For instance, in the Joe Slovo Park informal settlement in Cape Town, South Africa, from 52 illegal dump sites the majority are found along the roadsides (Jakeni et al., 2024).

Contributing factors to this practice include the lack or improper placement of community MSW bins, insufficient MSW collection infrastructure and transport vehicles, convenience, lack of enforcement, lack of a consistent waste disposal system and the assumption that solid waste disposal will be handled by others. This issue is prevalent in both rural and urban settings in Ethiopia, presenting a considerable challenge for municipal authorities (Shiferaw et al., 2023). Illegal dumping sites are prevalent throughout the sub-city, underscoring significant shortcomings in SWM. Despite some efforts to address the issue, these measures often prove insufficient, forcing residents to living amidst growing piles of waste. The financial burden of cleaning illegal dumpsites is significantly higher than regular solid waste collection, straining municipal resources and complicating SWM efforts (Chandel et al., 2024).

A study by Hailu and Wondim, employed geospatial technology was to assess MSW disposal in Dessie town (Kebede & Ayenew, 2023). The findings indicated that 71% of the area was not suitable for solid waste disposal, whereas only 29% was considered appropriate. The study suggests relocating the current MSW

disposal site in Dessie to more suitable areas, particularly on the outskirts of the town, specifically to the southwest, northeast, southeast, and north, away from urban centers, places of worship, schools, and densely populated regions.

Based on the above findings, Buanbuawuha sub-city has a good opportunities' to construct sustainable MSW disposal site. Because of the Sub-City, located in the northeast of Dessie, encompasses Tita, one of its five kebeles, which offers a large land area and a comparatively small population, making it an ideal location for such a facility.

MSW Collection and Transportation Methods

Different solid waste collections methods used in the Buanbuawuha sub-city. The most popular method is curbside or roadside collection (57.8%), which is common in suburban areas because it's convenient, allowing residents to place their trash near the curb for pickup. It's also efficient since one vehicle can collect solid waste from many homes quickly. However, in crowded urban areas or places without space for curbside bins, it is difficult to manage. If the solid waste isn't collected on time, it may attract pests or be scattered by the wind. The findings reveal that most people in the study area dispose of their solid waste by leaving it at the curbside rather than in designated areas. However, in the context of Buanbuawuha sub-city it often takes 3 to 4 days before the solid waste is transported. Because of these most of the community dispose their solid waste whether in road side or river side, leading to environmental unhealthiness(Oyareme et al., 2021)

The communal collection method is the second most common, particularly relevant in areas with limited resources. While communal collection can be a cost-effective, it faces challenges such as accessibility, cleanliness, and community engagement(Wang et al., 2018). The findings from Dessie suggest that although communal collection remains a viable option, it is less preferred than individualized collection methods. This highlights a potential area for improvement in local SWM strategies, where

enhancing the quality and efficiency of communal services could lead to better outcomes.

The door-to-door collection method also plays a role in solid waste collection in the sub-city, with smaller participants reflecting a hybrid approach to local SWM. A broader global trend where door-to-door services are, favored for their convenience and efficiency in urban SWM. Studies has shown that this method not only increases collection rates but also enhances community participation and recycling efforts by providing easier access to solid waste separation(Kebede & Ayenew, 2023). This method may serve as an effective compromise in areas where households are more spread out, allowing for efficient waste collection. Local studies further support these findings. Research conducted by Tassie et al. in nearby regions emphasizes the effectiveness of door-to-door collection in fostering public satisfaction and compliance with solid waste disposal practices(Tassie et al., 2024) Additionally, it was found that communities with tailored MSWM strategies, including door-to-door collection, demonstrated significantly higher rates of solid waste separation and recycling compared to those relying on communal methods(Jothimani et al., 2022).

The distribution of MSW transportation methods in the study area, revealing three primary methods: vehicles, hand/man powered carts and daily laborers. This distribution reflects the complex interplay between technological advancement, urban infrastructure, and socioeconomic factors in MSWM systems. MSW transportation methods vary significantly across regions, influenced by local infrastructure, economic conditions, and technological adoption(Ferronato & Torretta, 2019). The significant reliance on vehicles 50% indicates a higher level of mechanization compared to historical trends, suggesting potential improvements in collection efficiency and coverage. The use of hand/man powered carts and daily laborers aligns with the concept of decentralized collection systems, which are often more adaptable to diverse urban layouts and solid waste generation patterns. This mixed

approach combining mechanized and manual methods may offer a balance between efficiency and employment generation, particularly relevant in developing urban contexts (Aparcana, 2017).

However, insights from stakeholder discussions revealed a lack of a consistent transportation system in the sub-city is primarily due to a shortage of vehicles. It can be estimated that the daily MSW generated in the Buanbuawuha sub-city is around 61.56 tons/day based on the waste generation rate of 0.53 kg/person/day. Side-loading garbage truck chassis are designed to handle payloads of 5 tons (UN-HABITAT, 2010). This shows it has to make at least more than 12 trips a day to clean all the MSW generated. While it's not possible for a garbage truck to run more than 3 trips a day due to the distance and collection procedures of the scattered MSW. Therefore, at least 4 to 5 garbage trucks are needed to transport the MSW per day. However, there is no garbage truck governed by the sub-city, only one garbage truck has in town which is seriously insufficient. This means that, solid waste remained at the collection site for minimum of 3 or to 4 days. Additionally, manual laborers and daily workers often resort to dumping waste at nearby illegal sites, because the workload is overwhelming.

Municipal Solid Waste Management Practices

In Buanbuawuha, 87.8% of respondents stated that not engaging in source reduction practices, highlighting a significant area for improvement in MSWM, as effective source reduction can reduce solid waste generation at the outset (KUMAR et al., 2021). The findings highlight critical gaps in MSW recycling, reduction and sustainable solid waste practices reflecting broader problems in developing MSWM systems. The lack of source reduction practices among the respondents underscores an urgent need for educational campaigns and policies to encourage solid waste minimization at the generation stage. Communities with effective source reduction strategies often see a significant decrease in waste volumes, emphasizing the potential impact of targeted interventions.

The study also found alarmingly low recycling efforts, with 98.8% of respondents not recycling, indicating a lack of awareness and participation in recycling programs. Effective recycling can reduce solid waste volumes and promote sustainability. The negligible recycling efforts, with the respondents not participating, reveal a pressing need for awareness programs and infrastructure development to facilitate recycling. Recycling not only reduces the amount of MSW but also supports circular economy principles, creating value from waste materials (Bjerkli, 2013).

Similarly, the absence of reuse practices among 97.8% of respondents indicates untapped opportunities for waste diversion. Promoting reuse through public awareness campaigns and community programs can significantly contribute to solid waste reduction.

The high prevalence of burning or incineration reported by 51.5% of respondents, poses significant environmental and health hazards due to air pollution and toxic emissions. This finding highlights the need for alternative disposal methods and regulatory frameworks to manage waste safely and sustainably.

Additionally, the minimal adoption of composting, with 92.0% of respondents not practicing it, reflects missed opportunities for managing organic waste and improving soil health. In particular, according to the questionnaire survey results, the organic wastes accounts for 41% of the MSW and makes the proper treatment and disposal of them especially important to the overall waste management. Composting education programs and the provision of composting bins could encourage communities to turn organic solid waste into a valuable resource.

Energy Source Distribution per Households

The survey results highlight, a critical insight into energy usage and its environmental implications. As over 50% of respondents, still use on traditional and less clean energy sources. Electricity used by 48% of respondents is, the most common energy source but it can't be provided continuously. The respondents also use the rest of the energy because of insufficient

power of electricity. These include firewood, charcoal, dung, manure, gas, and kerosene, reflecting the ongoing reliance on non-renewable and polluting fuels. This not only hinders environmental sustainability but also perpetuates health risks associated with poor air quality. Integrating waste-to-energy (Ezemonye & Egharegbemi, 2022) solutions could provide a transformative opportunity. Converting organic solid waste into biogas expanding waste-to-energy infrastructure could also, mitigate MSWM challenges, and support a transition toward sustainable energy sources. The data reveals an urgent need to bridge the energy gap with environmentally friendly options.

The study found that organic waste made up the largest share of waste generated in the sub-city, totaling 344.31 kg per a day, for the surveyed 400 households with a daily generation rate of 0.861 kg per household. Ash also has significant contribution on MSW generation, with daily generating rate of 0.406 kg per household. This finding carries significant implications on MSWM, renewable energy production and composting. This organic solid waste represents a valuable resource for renewable energy production by converting it into biogas or other forms of energy through waste-to-energy technologies. On the other way, both ash and organic waste are highly beneficial for compost production due to their rich nutrient content and advantageous properties. The MSW generated in the sub-city has significant potential for both energy generation and fertilizer production. To use this potential, the sub-city could establish a biogas production plant in collaborating with local investors or partnering with the city administration. Additionally, organizing unemployed youth to engage in fertilizer production could create job opportunities as well as it's a way to handling MSW challenge. Since fertilizer is essential for supporting urban agricultural development, there is a strong market demand for it (Orsini et al., 2013). These efforts could foster sustainable practices and enhance the local economy. This approach not only reduces dependency on non-renewable and polluting energy sources but also fosters a circular economy, where waste becomes a resource instead of a liability.

Conclusion

This study has unveiled the complex and multifaceted challenges of SWM in Dessie town, particularly in the Buanbuawuha sub-city. It highlights critical shortcomings in infrastructure, unsustainable disposal practices, and a significant gap between environmental awareness and actionable behavior. The mean MSW generation rate was found to be 0.53 kg/person/day, with annual generation approaching 22,470 tons. Organic waste, comprising 40.9% of the total waste stream, is underutilized, while plastics and paper, over 31% of the total solid waste, are largely recyclable. The high reliance on traditional fuel sources and disposable materials exacerbates environmental degradation and public health threats. The absence of local MSW transportation vehicles leads to accumulation and illegal dumps, emphasizing the urgent need for improved waste collection systems and stricter enforcement of regulations.

The research revealed that socioeconomic factors such as family size and income levels influence solid waste generation patterns. An inverse correlation exists between household size and per capita solid waste generation, while a positive relationship is observed between income and MSW generation. To address these challenges, Buanbuawuha sub-city must prioritize a transformative approach to MSWM, investing in robust infrastructure, promoting waste-to-energy initiatives, and implementing public awareness campaigns. By tackling the underlying causes of MSWM and capitalizing on opportunities for resource recovery, the sub-city can foster a cleaner, healthier, and more sustainable urban environment.

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Conflict of interests

No conflict of interest.

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